

GEOHAB

Marine Geological and Biological
Habitat Mapping

GEOHAB 2010

Wellington, New Zealand

4-7 May 2010

*Characterisation, Quantification and
Diversity of Extreme Habitats*

**Conference Handbook
Programme & Abstracts**

Programme

MONDAY 3 MAY

09:30 to 15:30 : Pre-conference Workshop - IVS3D / ESRI : The use and benefits of the integrated application of Fledermaus and ArcGIS in Habitat Mapping	
17:00	Geohab 2010 Icebreaker and Registration
19:00	End of day

TUESDAY 4 MAY

08:30	Mihimihi (Traditional Maori Welcome)
08:40	Opening and Welcome
09:00	Keynote address: Andy Wheeler An Atlas of Ireland's Deep-water Seabed: the preview
09:30	Session 1 - Mapping metrics (Chair. Brian Todd)
10:10	Morning Tea
10:50	Session 1 - Mapping metrics, cont. (Chair. Vaughan Stagpoole)
12:30	Lunch
13:30	Session 1 - Mapping metrics, cont. (Chair. David Bowden)
15:10	Afternoon Tea
15:40	Session 1 - Mapping metrics, cont. (Chair. Andrew Heap)
17:00	Break
17:10	Special Meeting: Glossary (Chair. Mark Costello)
17:40	Special Session (S6): ATLAS (Chair. Peter Harris)
19:00	End of day

WEDNESDAY 5 MAY

08:30	Keynote address: Xavier Lurton Credibility of Sonar Backscatter Strength measurement, modelling and inversion
09:00	Session 2 - Statistical Analysis (Chair. Vanessa Lucieer)
10:20	Morning Tea
10:50	Session 2 - Statistical Analysis, cont. (Chair. Vladimir Kostylev)
12:30	Lunch
13:30	Session 2 - Statistical Analysis, cont. (Chair. Ian Wright)
13:50	Session 3 - Geo-Bio Interaction (Chair. Ian Wright)
15:10	Afternoon Tea
15:40	Session 3 - Geo-Bio Interaction, cont. (Chair. Judi Hewitt)
17:20	Break
18:30	Barbecue
22:00	End of day

THURSDAY 6 MAY

08:30	Keynote address: Malcolm Clark Habitat as a proxy for biodiversity: how can seamount classification systems aid the scientific design of marine protected areas
09:00	Session 3 - Geo-Bio Interaction, cont. (Chair. Bernard Pelletier)
10:20	Morning Tea
10:50	Session 4 - Vulnerable Habitat (Chair. Miquel Canals)
12:30	Lunch
13:30	Session 5 - National Programmes (Chair. Nic Bax)
15:10	Afternoon Tea
15:40	Session 5 - National Programmes, cont. (Chair. Gary Greene)
16:40	Break
17:10	Wrap-up discussion - AGM
18:10	End of day

FRIDAY 7 MAY

07:50 to 18:00 : Field Trip Discover faults, rocks, food and wine	
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GEOHAB 2010
Wellington New Zealand

Wellington Town Hall, 4 – 7 May 2010

GEOHAB 10th International Conference:

**Characterisation, Quantification and
Diversity of Extreme Habitats**

**Conference Handbook
Programme and Abstracts**

Geoffroy Lamarche
(Convenor and Committees' Chair)

Organising Committee

Suze Baird
David Bowden
Malcolm Clark
Martin Cryer
Andrew Heap
Judi Hewitt
Cathy Joanne
Yves Lafoy
Vanessa Lucieer
Alison MacDiarmid
Alan Orpin
Ashley Rowden
Janet Simes
Vaughan Stagpoole

Scientific Committee

Tara Anderson
Gary Greene
Andrew Heap
Kerstin Kroger
Yves Lafoy
Vanessa Lucieer
Xavier Lurton
Ashley Rowden
Terje Thorsnes
Brian Todd

<http://www.geohab.org>

ORGANISING COMMITTEE

Local Organising Committee

- Geoffroy Lamarche Chair, NIWA
- Suze Baird NIWA
- David Bowden NIWA
- Malcolm Clark NIWA
- Martin Cryer Ministry of Fisheries
- Andrew Heap Geoscience Australia
- Judi Hewitt NIWA
- Yves Lafoy Government of New Caledonia
- Vanessa Lucieer TAFI, University of Tasmania
- Alison MacDiarmid NIWA
- Alan Orpin NIWA
- Vaughan Stagpoole GNS Science
- Ashley Rowden NIWA

International Scientific Committee

- Geoffroy Lamarche Chair, NIWA
- Tara Anderson Geoscience Australia
- Gary Greene Moss Landing Marine Labs, USA
- Andrew Heap Geoscience Australia
- Kerstin Kroger Institute of Marine Research, Norway
- Yves Lafoy Government of New Caledonia
- Vanessa Lucieer TAFI, University of Tasmania
- Xavier Lurton Ifremer
- Ashley Rowden NIWA
- Terje Thorsnes Geological Survey of Norway, NGU
- Brian Todd Natural Resources Canada

Conference Manager

- Janet Simes Absolutely Organised Ltd.

Handbook Formatting, Secretariat

- Lisa Bragg NIWA
- Cathy Joanne NIWA/GeoAzur

Welcome to Geohab 2010

Nau mai, haere mai ki Te Whanganui-a-Tara, ki Aotearoa.

A very warm welcome to the 10th GeoHab meeting in Wellington, New Zealand!

During this three day conference you will be able to hear 55 scientists presenting their work and discuss around more than 50 posters. Each day will commence by an exclusive keynote presentation - which should properly wake you up and tune your mind for the day. The science programme promises to address a wide range of issues associated with habitat mapping in the largest sense of the term!

I want to thank particularly the local scientific committee who has put an extraordinary effort in organising this event. Together, we tried eagerly to remain within the spirit of Geohab, that is a one-session-fits-all and ample time for discussion and socialising, yet without compromising whatsoever the quality of the science. Our passion and dedication is in fundamental research science and is what should be celebrated during these three days.

The support and financial contributions made by our sponsors and exhibitors has been absolutely critical to the organisation of the event, in particular our two Gold sponsors, Kongsberg Maritime and the Commonwealth Environment Research Facilities - Australian Marine Biodiversity Research Hub. Without their support, we would have had to give up on the beautiful location, the quality of the audio-visual or the social programme (but not the quality of the science presented!). Sponsors support is all the more impressive in these times of economic difficulties and insecurity. Please, take time to visit their booth and discuss with the exhibitors.

Wellington, the capital city of New Zealand is a vibrant place, located around a beautiful harbour. Everything you could possibly want in a city is within easy walking distance. For those of you with energy left after the science programme and social events, a walk around the waterfront or to the top of Mount Victoria would be my recommendation. I hope you will get time to enjoy the city the same way I have enjoyed it for the last 22 years.

Welcome all, enjoy the programme to the full and make the most of your time in Aotearoa-New Zealand.

Geoffroy Lamarche
Convenor, Geohab 2010

- KEY ATTRactions**
- Beehive and Parliament Buildings
 - Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa
 - Cable Car
 - Botanic Garden
 - Westpac Stadium
 - Museum of Wellington
 - Wellington Zoo
 - ZEALANDIA: The Karori Sanctuary Experience
 - Weta Cave
- TRANSPORT**
- Wellington Domestic & International Airport
 - Railway Station & national bus services
 - Inter-island Ferries
 - Local Bus Terminal
 - Cruise Ship Terminal
 - State Highways
 - One way streets
 - Pedestrian streets
- AMENITIES**
- Wellington Hospital
 - Public Toilets
 - Public Showers
 - Accessible Playground
 - Car Parking
 - Mobility Car Parks
 - Wheelchair Beach Access
 - Lifts
- ROUTES**
- Civic Square to Te Papa
 - Accessible Walkway & Writers Walk
 - Railway Station to Westpac Stadium
 - Accessible City Route

FOR MORE INFORMATION

on Wellington visit the i-SITE Visitor Centre, in Civic Square. They can assist you with all your enquiries and bookings for Wellington and around New Zealand. Phone +64 4 802 4860 or visit our website, WellingtonNZ.com

DRIVING DISTANCES

Wellington to Makara	25 mins	11 km
Wellington to Porirua	20 mins	21 km
Wellington to Petone	15 mins	13 km
Wellington to Lower Hutt	20 mins	16 km
Wellington to Upper Hutt	35 mins	33 km
Wellington to Greytown	1 hr 10 mins	76 km
Wellington to Martinborough	1 hr 15 mins	81 km
Wellington to Masterton	1 hr 35 mins	108 km

ATTRactions

- A Colonial Cottage Museum
- B National War Memorial & Carlton
- C New Zealand Cricket Museum
- D Mount Victoria Lookout
- E Embassy Theatre
- F Downstage Theatre
- G BATS Theatre
- H St James Theatre
- I The Film Archive
- J Freyberg Pool
- K Circa Theatre
- L The Opera House
- M Wellington Convention Centre
- N Wellington Town Hall

ACCOMMODATION

- 1 Brenwood Hotel (Kilbirnie)
- 2 Mercure Hotel Willis Street
- 3 Quality Hotel Wellington Central City
- 4 Grand Mercure Wellington
- 5 Century City Apartments
- 6 Wellywood Backpackers Wellington
- 7 YHA Wellington City
- 8 The Bay Plaza Hotel
- 9 Oritel
- 10 Copthorne Hotel Oriental Bay
- 11 Museum Hotel
- 12 At Home Wellington City
- 13 At Home Wellington City
- 14 Duxton Hotel Wellington
- 15 Nomads Capital
- 16 West Plaza Hotel
- 17 Holiday Inn Wellington
- 18 Apartment Hotel
- 19 Abel Tasman Hotel
- 20 James Cook Hotel
- 21 Grand Chancellor
- 22 Travelodge Wellington
- 23 CityLife Wellington
- 24 Lambton Heights
- 25 Inter Continental Wellington
- 26 Hotel Ibis Wellington
- 27 Quest on the Terrace
- 28 Novotel Wellington
- 29 Quest on Johnston
- 30 Holiday Inn Wellington
- 31 Downtown Backpackers
- 32 Bolton Hotel
- 33 Kingsgate Hotel Wellington

Wellington Town Hall

- 11: Civic Ante Room
- 12: Civic Suite 1
- 13: Civic Suite 2
- 14: Civic Suite 3
- 15: Link Bridge

SECOND FLOOR

FIRST FLOOR

- 9: Auditorium Gallery
- 10: West Gallery

GROUND FLOOR

- 1: Main entrance
- 2: Green Room
- 3: Square Affair 1
- 4: Square Affair 2
- 5: Auditorium
- 6: Ilott Theatre
- 7: West Court
- 8: Civic Square entrance

The **Marine Biodiversity Hub** is analysing the patterns and dynamics of marine biodiversity to determine the appropriate units and models for effectively predicting Australia's marine biodiversity. It is developing novel options and tools for managing Australia's marine biodiversity.

MARINE BIODIVERSITY RESEARCH

Prediction and Management of Australia's Marine Biodiversity

By 2012, Australia will have a National Representative System of Marine Protected Areas. The NRSMPA is a major step towards the conservation of Australia's marine biodiversity and with off-reserve management will provide a new standard in marine planning. The Marine Biodiversity Hub is developing the knowledge to characterise, predict and manage biodiversity inside and outside the reserve system. Together, the NRSMPA and off-reserve management provide the best option for long term protection and sustainable use of our marine biodiversity.

www.marinehub.org

Australian Government
Department of the Environment,
Water, Heritage and the Arts

Australian Government

AUSTRALIAN INSTITUTE
OF MARINE SCIENCE

The Marine Biodiversity Hub is funded through the Commonwealth Environment Research Facilities Program (CERF), administered through the Australian Government's Department of the Environment, Water, Heritage and the Arts. The key aim of CERF is to provide sound advice to inform environmental public policy objectives and to better the management of Australia's unique environment. (Our stakeholder partners are: AFMA, APPEA, CFA, DAFF, DEWHA, DAFF, the Tourism CRC, and WWF Australia)

Marine Biodiversity Hub Partners

CSIRO > www.csiro.au/wfo

CSIRO is Australia's national science agency and is involved in the CERF Marine Biodiversity Hub through its Wealth from Oceans Flagship. The Flagship's marine conservation and biodiversity research will provide scientific understanding and management tools to underpin conservation of Australia's marine biodiversity in Commonwealth and state waters.

Geoscience Australia > www.ga.gov.au

Geoscience Australia is Australia's national geoscience research agency. One of the key activities of the agency is to create, maintain and disseminate geographic and geological knowledge to provide information about the marine jurisdiction for environmental, economic and social purposes.

Museum Victoria > www.museum.vic.gov.au

Museum Victoria provides expertise in taxonomy of marine invertebrates that is critical for understanding the biodiversity, biogeography and evolution of Australia's biota.

Tasmanian Aquaculture and Fisheries Institute – University of Tasmania > www.utas.edu.au/tafi/

The Tasmanian Aquaculture and Fisheries Institute is a partnership between the University and the Tasmanian Government that supports the development and sustainable management of living marine resources in the region. Research is centred around three programs: Sustainable Fisheries, Estuaries & Coasts and Sustainable Aquaculture.

Australian Institute of Marine Science > www.aims.gov.au

The Australian Institute of Marine Science (AIMS) generates and transfers knowledge to support the sustainable use and protection of the tropical marine environment through innovative, world class research. The Institute is a leader in tropical marine science with strong national and international collaborative links. AIMS has highly developed capabilities in marine biodiversity, impacts and adaptation to climate change, water quality and ecosystem health and has established a new research direction in marine microbiology. The Institute's research programs support the management of tropical marine environments around the globe, with an emphasis on the Great Barrier Reef World Heritage Area, northwest Australia and Ningaloo Marine Park in Western Australia.

Hub Stakeholders

Australian Fisheries Management Authority	www.afma.gov.au
Australian Petroleum Production and Exploration Association Limited	www.appea.com.au
Commonwealth Fisheries Association	
Department of the Environment, Water, Heritage and the Arts	www.environment.gov.au
Department of Agriculture, Fisheries and Forestry	www.daff.gov.au
Sustainable Tourism CRC	www.crctourism.com.au
World Wildlife Fund Australia	www.wwf.org.au

MARINE BIODIVERSITY RESEARCH

Prediction and Management of Australia's Marine Biodiversity

Marine Survey Services

- Hydrographical mapping
- Pipeline & cable route surveys
- ROV & ROTV inspection
- Environmental studies
- Archaeological surveys
- Mine & munition detection
- Geotechnical investigations
- River & lake surveys
- Biological services
- Site surveys
- Wreck investigations

MMT is a Swedish survey company with 200 employed specialists within the field of marine survey.

MMT

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GENERAL INFORMATION

Venue

The venue for the conference is the Civic Suites, Level 2, Wellington Town Hall, located in the Wellington Convention Centre at 111 Wakefield Street. The presentations will be in Civic 1 & 2 and the poster sessions and refreshment breaks will be held across in the Civic Foyer, the Lantern areas and foyer and Civic 3 (see plans).

Registration and Help Desk

The registration and information desk is located in the Lantern Foyer, Level 2, Wellington Town Hall, amongst the posters, trade displays and catering. There will also be a registration desk at the icebreaker.

The registration desk opens 30 minutes prior to the start of the sessions (9.00 am on Monday, 8.00 am on Tuesday, Wednesday and Thursday).

Please wear your name badge at all time.

Satchels and abstract volume

Abstract volumes are available on the USB drive provided in your folder. Pre-ordered bound copies will be delivered at registration.

Oral presentations

All oral presentations are 20 minute long (including questions), except for plenary talks, which are 30 minute long. There is only ONE screen available for presentations.

Presentations can be given as PowerPoint 2003 (*.ppt or *.pps) or PDF files only (note however that the Microsoft converter patch for Office 2007 will be loaded on all laptops, so that documents generated with the 2007 versions of Word, Excel and PowerPoint 2007 will be readable). Presentations must be uploaded onto the supplied laptops prior to each session and the start of the day.

Please use a standard font set. If you have movies or animations in your talk, you **MUST** check that your presentation functions on the supplied computers. Conference staff will be there to assist you.

Unless there are compelling logistical reasons why the supplied laptops are not suitable, presenters should not anticipate that they can plug their own laptops into the projector during the session. Should this be unavoidable, presenters must alert the session chair prior to commencement of the session.

Poster presentations

Poster sessions are held during the refreshment and lunch breaks, located in the Civic Suite Foyer, Civic Suite 3 and the Lantern Areas. Poster presenters are encouraged to stand by their poster during the morning and afternoon refreshment breaks on Wednesday 5 May.

Poster presentations must be no wider than 1.15m. The poster boards are 1.5 m high. Velcro dots will be available at the registration desk to secure the posters to the boards. Pins are not suitable.

Refreshments

Morning and afternoon refreshments and lunches are provided. These are served from two locations – please use both throughout the conference and visit the trade exhibits throughout the Civic Foyer, the Lantern Areas and Civic Suite 3.

Communication / Internet

A comprehensive wireless internet network is available for use throughout all venues. A voucher for 24 hours access with unlimited traffic can be purchased for \$10 per 24 hours at the Michael Fowler Centre reception. This cost is NOT covered by your registration to Geohab 2010.

Hardwire broadband is also available but will incur a \$100 set up fee and \$50 per day hire. This cost is NOT covered by your registration to Geohab 2010.

In respect for the presenters, please refrain from using your laptop in the conference room. Remember to turn you mobile phones OFF.

Student Award

Students must collect their cheques from Gary Greene.

Transport and Parking

Car parking in town is tight, but usually available in the Michael Fowler Centre Car Park, the James Smith Car Park adjacent to the Duxton Hotel, Lombard Street car park and Queens Wharf Event Centre car park. Daily parking costs are \$15-25.

Transport to and from the airport

Use a bus (Airport Flyer, ~ \$8), door-to-door shuttle (~\$15) or taxi (~\$30) to go from the airport to the city and back. Most taxis will accept major credit cards.

There are five rental car agencies that have desks at ground level of the main terminal in Wellington Airport.

Check <http://www.wellington-airport.co.nz/html/parkingtransport/bus.php>

As many of you will arrive at the same time at Wellington Airport, sharing a taxi may prove cost efficient and environmentally friendly!

Dining out in Wellington

Wellington has the highest concentration of cafés and restaurants of any city in New Zealand. The downtown area can cater for just about any taste. There are a number of restaurants in Blair and Allen Streets around 500 m east of the conference venue. There are also many restaurants in Cuba Street to the south. Expect to pay around NZD\$18-30 for a main dish (there is no gratuity). During the day there are several cafés within a 500 m radius of the town hall.

Wellington Weather

Wellington is situated at 41° south. Funnelling of wind through the nearby Cook Strait has provided the city with the legendary title of the world's windiest city. Weather is never still and never the same from one hour to the next. The way I see it: Wellington is a 5-dimensional city: w, x, y, z, t (w for wind).

May is the end of autumn. Days will be short (sunrise 7:15 am, sunset 5:30 pm) and daytime maximum temperatures can range from 17°C (63F) to 11° (52F). But wind chill can make these temperatures feel much cooler! Rain is likely but you can expect some bright and beautiful days too – New Zealand isn't green by mistake!

3 to 5 days forecast: <http://www.metservice.com/towns-cities/wellington>

Time

In May the time zone is New Zealand Standard Time (NZST), which is GMT/UTC + 12 hrs.

NIWA's ocean geology and ecology science and services

- **Our** science expertise helps manage New Zealand's marine resources to benefit the economy and protect the environment.
- **We** acquire bathymetry data and develop underpinning quantitative mapping methods for hydrographic surveying, habitat mapping, and resource assessment.
- **Our** seascape research focuses on fundamental geological processes to understand and mitigate natural hazards, such as active faults, submarine landslides, and volcanism.
- **We** combine systematic and taxonomic expertise to undertake environmental impact assessments and help meet the requirements of New Zealand's Biodiversity Strategy.
- **We** developed the New Zealand Marine Environment Classification (MEC), as an ecosystem-based spatial framework designed for marine management purposes.
- **Our** flagship research vessel *Tangaroa* supplies full logistical and scientific support throughout the Southern Ocean.
- **We** collaborate with leading research institutions worldwide allowing us to share and develop state-of-the-art equipment and scientific knowledge.

Contacts:

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SOCIAL PROGRAMME

Icebreaker - Monday 3 May, 17:00

An informal "Icebreaker" function will be held in conjunction with registration at **"Mac's Brewery Bar & Restaurant"**, corner of Taranaki and Cable Streets on the Wellington Waterfront. This will commence at 5:00-7.00 pm Monday 3 May and there will be an opportunity to catch up with fellow registrants. Snacks and refreshments will be served.

Mihimihi - Tuesday 4 May, 08:30

Whaikorero and mihimihi are traditional Maori speeches of welcome, which take place at the beginning of a gathering. The welcoming establishes links between the hosts (tangata whenua) and their visitors (manuwhiri). Mihimihi involve representatives from both the host and the visiting parties to stand and introduce themselves by sharing their whakapapa (genealogy, ancestral ties) and other relevant information. It is important for Māori to know and to share their whakapapa as to know one's whakapapa is to know one's identity.

The hosts will usually identify specific geographical features associated with their tribal area including their maunga (mountain), awa (river) and moana (sea). They may also identify their waka (ancestral canoe), hapū (sub tribe), iwi (tribe), marae and an eponymous ancestor. This information is considered more important than the individual's own name which may be the last piece of information given in mihimihi. They will also acknowledge the main reason for the conference and also what they hope to achieve.

Barbecue - Wednesday 5 May, 18:30

A barbecue will be held in the Wardroom located on the ground floor **Royal Port Nicholson Yacht Club**, 103 Oriental Bay, an easy walk from the Town Hall and most centrally located accommodation. This will commence at 6:30 pm and run through until about 10:00 pm. A full barbecue-type meal will be served and some refreshments provided. All registrants are welcome to attend but please wear your nametag as your entry ticket.

A cultural event will be performed during the BBQ.

Field Trip - Friday 7 May, 07:50

For those who chose to take the fieldtrip from our capital city to the peace of rural Wairarapa (Maori for "glistening waters"), you will experience some of the geology and natural history of New Zealand during the one and a half hour trip to the world-renown vineyard historic town of Martinborough in the center of Wairarapa. Here, you will taste premium wines from award-winning vineyards, learn about the terroir that makes this wine-making area so special, and share a succulent lunch before travelling to the wild southern coast of this region to explore the dramatic landforms known as the Putangirua Pinnacles.

See detail p. 29.

Australian Government
Geoscience Australia

Marine and Coastal *Environment Group*

As Australia's national geoscience research agency Geoscience Australia's mission is to use geoscientific information and knowledge for the economic, social and environmental benefit of Australia.

The Marine and Coastal Environment Group (MCEG) within Geoscience Australia's Petroleum and Marine Division provides geoscientific advice and products as required by government to meet its goals in the implementation of the National Ocean's Policy within Australia's EEZ.

The Group's work addresses Government priorities for preservation and maintenance of biodiversity, ecosystem based management and support of offshore petroleum exploration.

The Group is also responsible for determining the location of Australia's marine boundaries and provides information to government in relation to the limits of the extended continental shelf as defined by the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS).

Further information about the Group's activities can be found on our webpage:
www.ga.gov.au/marine

A list of publications can be found at:
www.ga.gov.au/oceans/mc_smac_pubs.jsp

FOR FURTHER INFORMATION CONTACT:

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GPO Box 378 Canberra ACT 2601

APPLYING GEOSCIENCE TO AUSTRALIA'S MOST IMPORTANT CHALLENGES

SPECIAL SESSIONS

Special Glossary Meeting – Tuesday 4 May, 17:10

“Towards an international marine geo-bio-ecological glossary...”

Chair: Mark Costello (University of Auckland)

"Standardised terminology facilitates readers understanding of publications, from maps to science papers; reduces new alternative uses of words and their perpetuation and resulting confusion; and enables the comparison of data across datasets by researchers. This session proposes to establish a process involving volunteer scientists to develop a recommended glossary for marine habitat and related ecological and geological terminology.

This process will include a small editorial group who will prepare a first version, using existing glossaries and their own. This will (a) include comments about alternative uses of words, and (b) be published online where users can submit questions about definitions and propose additional words to be defined. The final product and continuing process would seek endorsement by major international initiatives, such as IOC, IODE, EoL, GBIF, TDWG, IHO and others. This session is the first call for contributors and editors to begin this process."

Special ATLAS session (Session 6) – Tuesday 4 May, 17:40

“Geohab Atlas of seafloor geomorphic features and benthic habitats”

Chair: Peter Harris (Geoscience Australia)

The work of GeoHab scientists demonstrates how habitat maps compiled for different seabed geomorphic features can be used as surrogates for the benthic communities that they typically support. In this way, conservation priorities can be identified using geomorphic feature and seabed habitat maps as a guide. Knowledge of the geomorphology and biogeography of the seafloor has improved markedly over the past 10 years. Using multibeam sonar, the benthic ecology of submarine features such as fjords, sand banks, coral reefs, seamounts, canyons, mud volcanoes and spreading ridges has been revealed in unprecedented detail. Habitat maps of these features are created when acoustic data are coupled with seabed video and biological sampling, thus providing a powerful tool for understanding benthic ecosystems and spatial patterns of biodiversity.

In this session, 12 case studies will be presented from the >60 studies offered for publication in a new book sponsored by GeoHab and scheduled for publication by Elsevier in 2011. The case studies will represent a range of seabed features where detailed bathymetric maps have been combined with seabed video and sampling to yield an integrated picture of the communities that are associated with different types of benthic habitat.

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Courtesy of SHOM

NOAA Ship Okeanos Explorer, 'America's Ship for Ocean Explora- tion' makes a major discovery using the Kongsberg Multibeam System EM 302

The NOAA Ship Okeanos Explorer is the only United States ship assigned to explore systematically our largely unknown ocean for the purpose of discovery and the advancement of knowledge. On its first voyage using the EM 302 it made a major discovery of what are believed to be methane gas plumes.

EM 302 water column data detected plumes located in location identified above while transiting to the Cordell Bank National Marine Sanctuary working grounds from Astoria, Oregon. The plumes were located in water depths between 1200 and 1900 meters. All plumes were observed to rise to a water depth between 500-550 m making their heights between 700-1400 meters.

NOAA EM 302 Image of Plumes using IVS3D Fledermaus

NOAA Ship 'Okeanos Explorer'

Interactive Visualization Systems (IVS3D) developed the Fledermaus mid water software tool as part of a project with the Center for Coastal and Ocean Mapping (CCOM)/ Joint Hydrographic Center (JHC) of the University of New Hampshire. Fledermaus was made available to this project.

Dr. Jim Gardner and Mashoor Malik (CCOM/JHC) suggest "that the plumes are made up of a stream of methane bubbles coated with a veneer of methane-rich ice. That ice coating, a material called methane hydrate, is stable in deep water, where pressure is high and the water is cold. When the ice-cloaked bubbles ascend into warmer waters near the surface, the ice melts and the methane dissolves into the sea." "Although seafloor sediments in shallow areas closer to the coast are known to harbor methane, which often bubbles free of the ocean bottom, no one has reported such plumes in waters this deep, the researchers report. The newly discovered plume appears to originate within a previously unknown, amphitheater-shaped basin on the ocean floor. This 3.6-kilometer-wide scar was probably caused by a massive undersea landslide"

Gardner, J. V., Malik, M. A., Walker, S. , 2009, "Plume 1400 Meters High Discovered at the Seafloor off the Northern California Margin", EOS Transactions, American Geophysical Union, Vol. 90, No. 32, pp. 275 - 275. Journal Article.

Next-Generation 3D Mapping System

"The Okeanos Explorer has been outfitted with a new Multibeam swath mapping system. The hull-mounted, first of its kind, Kongsberg EM 302 will provide explorers with high-resolution maps of the seafloor from 40 to 4000 meters. Maps from the system will be used to identify unique seafloor features for further exploration and will be integrated into the high-precision DVL-Nav navigation system to provide a road map for exploring a particular site with the ROV."

NOAA EM 302 Image of Amphitheater-Shaped Plume Basin

KONGSBERG

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- seabed seep analysis and chemistry
- hydrothermal plume and vent fluid chemistry
- UNCLOS advice

For more information contact:

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Wellington Town Hall - Level 2

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 - 5** : NIWA
 - 6** : Department of Conservation
 - 7** : University of Otago
 - 8/9** : Kongsberg
 - 10** : Seabed Mapping
 - 11** : Geoscience Australia
 - 12/13** : Marine Biodiversity Research (CERF/CSIRO)
 - 14** : Acoustic Imaging
 - 15** : ESRI
 - 16** : GNS Science

List of Sponsors and Exhibitors (in alphabetical order)

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IVS30 F l e d e r m a u s

**SOFTWARE FOR HABITAT
MAPPING AND MONITORING**

Pre-conference Workshop (only on registration)

All oral presentations in Civic Suites 1/2

Monday 3 May

		Monday 3 May	
Workshop	09:30	Welcome and Introduction to IVS-ESRI workshop by <u>Douglas Bergersen</u> (IVS3D)	
	09:45	ESRI Tools for Habitat Mapping by <u>Jaime Crandall</u> (ESRI)	
	10:15	IVS Tools for Habitat Mapping by <u>Lindsay Gee</u> (IVS3D)	
Bk	10:45	Tea Break (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)	
Workshop	11:00	Use of the ARC Marine Data Model in the context of Habitat Mapping by <u>Jaime Crandall</u> (ESRI)	
	11:30	IVS-ESRI Habitat Mapping Workflow applied to the NIWA Cook Strait data set by <u>Douglas Bergersen</u> (IVS3D)	
Break	12:00	Lunch Break (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)	
Workshop	13:00	Case Example 1 by <u>Jens Greinhart</u> (Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research)	
	13:40	Case Example 2 by <u>Arne Pallentin</u> (National Institute of Water and Atmospheric Research, NZ)	
	14:20	Case Example 3 by <u>Scott Nichol</u> (Geoscience Australia)	
	15:00	Final Comments and questions by <u>Douglas Bergersen</u> (IVS3D)	
Break	15:30	Tea Break (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)	
	16:00		
Social Event	17:00	Geohab 2010 Icebreaker and Registration 17:00-19:00, Mac's Brewery Bar & Restaurant	

All oral presentations in Civic Suites 1/2

Tuesday 4 May

Reg.	08:00	Conference Registration open
Welcome	08:30	Mihimihi (Traditional Maori Welcome)
	08:40	Opening and Welcome
Keynote	09:00	KEYNOTE ADDRESS: "An Atlas of Ireland's Deep-water Seabed: the preview" by <u>Andy Wheeler</u> , Boris Dorschel, Xavier Monteys and Koen Verbruggen
S1 - Mapping Chair: Brian Todd	09:30	"A picture on the wall: 3D habitat mapping in deep-sea canyons" by <u>Veerle A.I. Huvenne</u> , Doug G. Masson, Paul A. Tyler, Veit Hühnerbach and the ISIS ROV Team
	09:50	STUDENT AWARD: "A system for mapping nearshore, marine habitats on a tight budget" by <u>Kelly C. Kingon</u>
Break	10:10	Tea Break and Posters (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)
S1 - Mapping Metrics Chair: Vaughan Stagpoole	10:50	"Seafloor sediment classification in a tidal inlet channel: The influence of shell debris and seafloor rugosity" by <u>Dietmar Bürk</u> , Martina Heineke, H. Christian Hass, Ralf Vorberg and Rolf Riethmüller
	11:10	"Geo-statistical mapping of sediment composition with application to habitat classification" by David Stephens, <u>Markus Diesing</u> and Roger Coggan
	11:30	"Deep-Water Forage Habitats - The Next Step Forward in Marine Benthic Habitat Mapping?" by <u>H. Gary Greene</u> , J. Vaughn Barrie and Tina Wyllie-Echeverria
	11:50	"Geoacoustic mapping of cold seep habitats along the Hikurangi margin, New Zealand" by <u>Ingo Klaucke</u> , Andrew T. Jones, Wilhelm Weinrebe, David Bowden and C. Jörg Petersen
	12:10	"Seamount habitat mapping on the Condor Bank (Azores, NE Atlantic)" by <u>Fernando Tempera</u> , E. Giacomello, F. Porteiro, A. Martins, I. Bashmachnikov, A. Henriques, J. Nuno Pereira, T. Morato, D. Catarino, R. Santos and G. Menezes
Break	12:30	Lunch Kindly sponsored by IMarest Served in Civic Suite 3 and Foyer

S1 - Mapping Metrics	Chair: David Bowden	13:30	"The role of physical environmental variables in shaping seabed biodiversity patterns" by <u>Roland Pitcher</u> , Nick Ellis, Peter Lawton, Stephen Smith, Chi-Lin Wei, Lew Incze, Michelle Greenlaw, Jess Sameoto, Nick Wolff, Tom Shirley and Gil Rowe
		13:50	"Mapping and Predicting Benthic Habitats, Biological Assemblages, and Biodiversity across the Carnarvon Shelf, Western Australia" by <u>Tara J. Anderson</u> , Andrew Heyward, Scott Nichols, Matthew McArthur, Christine Schoenberg, Jamie Colquhoun, Zhi Huang, Maggie Tran and Brendan Brooke
		14:10	"Multibeam sonar in the deep-sea: can it really tell us much about benthic habitats and fauna?" by <u>David Bowden</u> , Judi Hewitt, Anne-Laure Verdier and Arne Pallentin
		14:30	"Habitat-based assessment of epibenthos using AUV Optical imagery, northwest Australia" by <u>Jamie Colquhoun</u> , Oscar Pizarro, Andrew Heyward, Max Rees, Stefan Williams, Rebecca O'leary and Ben Radford
		14:50	"A GIS analysis of New Zealand's Trawl Footprint" by <u>Jenny Black</u> and Ray Wood
Break		15:10	Tea Break and Posters (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)
S1 - Mapping Metrics	Chair: Andrew Heap	15:40	"A geospatial approach to coral reef geomorphology" by <u>Javier Leon</u> , Colin Woodroffe, Kevin Parnell and Scott Smithers
		16:00	"A comparison of fish diversity estimates made by stereo-video systems and traps at depths ranging from 50 to 900m" by <u>Vincent Zintzen</u> , Clive Roberts, Andrew Stewart, Marti J. Anderson and Euan Harvey
		16:20	"Application of an Integrated GIS and 4D Visualisation Tool Kit to the NIWA Cook Strait Data Set" by <u>Douglas Bergersen</u> , Moe Doucet, Lindsay Gee and Robin Smith
		16:40	"Making Technology Transparent - A key to better science is spending more time studying the data than collecting it" by <u>Francois Leroy</u>
Bk		17:00	Break
Special Meeting	Mark Costello	17:10	Special Glossary Meeting: "Towards an international marine geo-bio-ecological glossary" (See details in General Information, p. 17)
S6 - ATLAS	Chair: Peter Harris	17:40	Special ATLAS Session: "Geohab Atlas of seafloor geomorphic features and benthic habitats" (See details in General Information, p. 17) (~ 90 min)
		19:10	

All oral presentations in Civic Suites 1/2

Wednesday 5 May	
Reg.	08:00 Conference Registration open
Keynote	08:30 KEYNOTE ADDRESS: "Credibility of sonar Backscatter Strength measurement, modelling and inversion" by <u>Xavier Lurton</u> and Jean-Marie Augustin
S2 - Statistical Analysis Chair: Vanessa Lucieer	09:00 "Can oceanographic conditions explain species distribution patterns on the Chatham Rise and Challenger Plateau" by <u>Kathryn Julian</u> , Tanya J. Compton and David Bowden
	09:20 "Some issues in predicting biodiversity using spatially modelled covariates" by <u>Hideyasu Shimadzu</u> , Scott D. Foster and Ross Darnell
	09:40 "Spatial predictability of species diversity and abundance of epimacrobenthos in turbid nearshore using bathymetric LiDAR" by <u>Antoine Collin</u> , Bernard Long and Philippe Archambault
	10:00 "Modelling species distributions: the application of predicted habitat models to define demersal fish distributions" by <u>Cordelia H. Moore</u> , Ben Radford, Euan S. Harvey and Kimberly Van Niel
Break	Tea Break and Posters (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)
S2 - Statistical Analysis Chair: Vladimir Kostylev	10:50 "Towards Automated Classification of Benthic Environments using Rugosity, Slope and Aspect from Bathymetric Stereo Image Reconstructions" by <u>Ariell Friedman</u> (STUDENT AWARD), Oscar Pizarro and Stefan Williams
	11:10 "Object based segmentation of multibeam backscatter data: methods for spatial analysis of shallow coastal seabeds, South Eastern Tasmania, Australia" by <u>Vanessa Lucieer</u> , Nicole Hill and Neville Barrett
	11:30 "Deriving "mappable" biological assemblages from underwater footage using classification tree models" by <u>Genoveva Gonzalez-Mirelis</u> (STUDENT AWARD), and Mats Lindegarth
	11:50 "Image-based habitat classification and analysis using generative models" by <u>Oscar Pizarro</u> , Stefan Williams, Jamie Colquhoun and Cordelia Moore
	12:10 "Automated delineation of acoustic themes from Multibeam backscatter data for seafloor characterization, Tapuae Marine Reserve, NZ" by <u>Alexandre C.G. Schimel</u> , Yuri Rzhonov, Luciano Fonseca, Larry Mayer, Terry R. Healy and Dirk Immenga
Break	12:30 Lunch Kindly sponsored by Gardline Environmental Served in Civic Suite 3 and Foyer

S2	S3 - Geo-Bio Interaction Chair: Ian Wright	13:30	"Predicting Groups of Species: application of finite mixture models to species prediction" by Piers K. Dunstan, Scott D. Foster and Ross Darnell
		13:50	"Environmental classifications, acoustic remote assessment and ecosystem valuing" by Judi E. Hewitt, Joanne Ellis, David Bowden and Ian Tuck
		14:10	"Diversity in benthic habitats and sediments at Great Barrier Island, New Zealand" by Tuan Meng Lee (STUDENT AWARD), Kala Sivaguru, Roger Grace, Timothy J. Langlois and Mark J. Costello
		14:30	"Geomorphological characterisation of cold water corals habitats (Bay of Biscay, NE Atlantic)" by Jean-Francois Bourillet, Thierry Schmitt, Alessandra Savini, Brigitte Guillaumont and Sophie Arnaud-Haond
		14:50	"The Catalan submarine canyon heads, NW Mediterranean Sea: coupling seafloor morphology and biological diversity" by Miquel Canals, Galderic Lastras, David Amblas, Ben De Mol and "Euroleón" Cruise Shipboard Party
Break		15:10	Tea Break and Posters (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)
S3 - Geo-Bio Interaction Chair: Judi Hewitt		15:40	"GIS-Mapping of Marine Benthic Habitats using Expert-based and Statistical Methodologies" by Roland Pesch, Susanne Ranft, Marc Busch and Winfried Schroder
		16:00	"Relationships between seabed assemblages in the Gulf of Maine and their physical environment using Random Forests" by Peter Lawton, Stephen J. Smith, Lewis S. Incze, Michelle E. Greenlaw, Nicholas H. Wolff, Jessica Sameoto, Roland Pitcher, Nick Ellis
		16:20	"Geostatistical and landscape analysis of fine-scale eelgrass (<i>Zostera marina</i>) habitat patterns" by Jeffrey Barrell (STUDENT AWARD) and Jon Grant
		16:40	"Dynamics of benthic patch structure across two seasons in a coastal embayment" by Zhi Huang, Lynda Radke and Matthew Mearthar
		17:00	"Physical controls on deep-water coral communities on the George V margin, East Antarctica" by Alexandra L. Post, P.E. O'brien, R.J. Beaman and M.J. Riddle
Break		17:20	Break
Social Event		18:30	Barbecue 18:30-22:00, Royal Port Nicholson Yatch Club

All oral presentations in Civic Suites 1/2

Thursday 6 May

Reg.	08:00	Conference Registration open
Keynote	08:30	KEYNOTE ADDRESS: "Habitat as a proxy for biodiversity: how can seamount classification systems aid the scientific design of marine protected areas" by <u>Malcolm R. Clark</u> , Ashley A. Rowden, Les Watling, John M. Guinotte and Craig R. Smith
S3 - Geo-Bio Interactions Chair: Bernard Pelletier	09:00	"Environmental - biological covariance in the soft sediments surrounding Lord Howe Island" by <u>Matthew McArthur</u> , Hideyasu Shimadzu and Brendan Brooke
	09:20	"The Influence of Physical Parameters on Benthic Communities – A Case Study in the Gulf of Finland, the Baltic Sea" by <u>Anna-Leena Downie</u> and Anu M. Kaskela
	09:40	"Spatial prediction of demersal fish habitat suitability from remotely-sensed observation and hydroacoustic datasets" by <u>Jacquomo Monk</u> , D. Ierodiaconou, A. Bellgrove, E. Harvey, A. Rattray, L. Laurenson and G. Quinn
	10:00	"Quantifying trawling impacts on deep-sea ecosystems using ROV video and scanning-sonar data" by <u>Maeva Gauthier</u> , S. Kim Juniper, J. Vaughn Barrie, Rosaline R. Canessa and James A. Boutillier
Break	10:20	Tea Break and Posters (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)
S4 - Vulnerable Habitat Chair: Miquel Canais	10:50	"Identifying ecologically and biologically significant deepwater habitat" by <u>Nicholas J. Bax</u> and Alan Williams
	11:10	"Using GIS Models to Delimit Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem (VME) Boundaries in the Northwest Atlantic Regulatory Area (NRA)" by <u>Andrew T. Cogswell</u> , Ellen L.R. Kenchington and Camille G. Lirette
	11:30	"Predictive cold-water coral habitat mapping in the Western Mediterranean Sea" by <u>Ben De Mol</u> , David Amblas, Miquel Canais, Galderic Lastras, Anna Sanchez, Antonio Calafat, and Darwin Cd178, Euroleon and Hermesione Shipboard Party
	11:50	"The alkaline hydrothermal field of the Prony Bay, Southern New Caledonia" by <u>Bernard Pelletier</u> and Claude E. Payri
	12:10	"Seabed habitats of the Beaufort Sea Shelf (Canadian Arctic)" by <u>Vladimir E. Kostylev</u> , Kerstin Jerosch and Steve Blasco
Break	12:30	Lunch Break and Posters (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)

S5 - National Programmes	Chair: Nic Bax	13:30	"Mapping habitat and biological diversity in coastal ecosystems: Bay of Islands, New Zealand" by <u>Mark Morrison</u> , & the NIWA Ocean Survey 20/20 Project Team
		13:50	"Mesophotic Coral Ecosystems of Puerto Rico" by <u>Roy A. Armstrong</u> and Hanumant Singh
		14:10	"Seabed mapping for Australia's energy security" by <u>Andrew D. Heap</u> , Rachel Przeslawski, Scott Nichol, Lynda Radke, Chris Battershill and Stephen Whalan
		14:30	"Mapping and modelling spatial distribution of important nature types such as kelp forest, sea grass beds and shell sand, procedures and results from a national mapping program in Norway with focus on the Skagerrak region" by <u>Eli Rinde</u> , J. Gitmark, H. Christie, W. Eikrem, H. Olsen, R. Bøe, H. Steen and T. Bodvin
		14:50	"Phanerogame meadows: a characteristic habitat of the Mediterranean shelf. Examples from the Tyrrhenian Sea" by <u>Silvana D'angelo</u> and Andrea Fiorentino
Break		15:10	Tea Break and Posters (Civic Suite 3 and Foyer)
S5 - National Prog.	Chair: Gary Greene	15:40	"Habitat Mapping in Aitutaki, Cook Islands" by <u>Ashishika Sharma</u> (STUDENT AWARD), Jens Krüger, Satesh Kumar, Chris Roelfsema and Ngere George
		16:00	"ZoNeCo: a multidisciplinary approach to Marine Habitats in New Caledonia" by <u>Yves Lafoy</u> , A. Rivaton and D Buisson
		16:20	"Mapping and modelling seabed nature-types in Norway's MAREANO programme – lessons learned" by <u>Margaret F.J. Dolan</u> , Pål Buhl-Mortensen, Kim Picard, Terje Thorsnes, Sigrid Elvenes, Valérie K. Bellec, Lene Buhl-Mortensen and Reidulv Bøe
Break		16:40	Break
Discussion		17:10	Wrap-up discussion (~1h) AGM

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Friday 7 May

FIELD TRIP :
Discover faults, rocks, food and wine

07:50	Please assemble near the Wellington Town Hall The Transit coach will be parked in Wakefield Street, outside the Wellington Town Hall, opposite the West Plaza Hotel.
08:00	Depart Wellington, driving past the Parliament Buildings and “The Beehive” before heading north on the motorway that travels alongside the Wellington Fault (optional stop on the Wellington Fault outcrop). After skirting Wellington Harbour, we travel up the Hutt River valley, then across the spectacular Rimutaka Hill Road (summit 550 m) to the Wairarapa region, with stops to inspect the sights.
10:15	Meet our Zest guide at the entrance to the Martinborough Wine Village, then visit Martinborough Vineyard – one of the founding vineyards and wineries in the district – meet the viticulturist and/or winemaker and taste the wine’s terroir in the glass, especially the Pinot Noir for which the district is renowned.
12:00	Lunch at Coney Wines, a winery and cafe about 10 minutes south of Martinborough Village. Relax and refuel with good food and wine.
13:45	Depart Coney Wines and travel to the South Coast of the North Island, to walk up Putangirua Stream (cut through ancient gravel layers) to see the striking Putangirua Pinnacles landforms (you might recognise them as a scene stealer in “Lord of the Rings”).
16:00	Leave the coast and return to Featherston via the East-West Access Road with glimpses of Lake Wairarapa, and back to Wellington over the Rimutaka Hill Road
18:00 (approx)	Arrive back in Wellington, at the Town Hall (Wakefield Street)

LIST OF TALKS

Authors	Title	Session	Date / Time
Allee et al.,	Two Shelf Edge Marine Protected Areas in the Eastern Gulf of Mexico	6	Tue, 17h40
Anderson et al.,	Mapping and Predicting Benthic Habitats, Biological Assemblages, and Biodiversity across the Carnarvon Shelf, Western Australia	1	Tue, 13h50
Armstrong et al.,	Mesophotic Coral Ecosystems of Puerto Rico	5	Thu, 13h50
Barrell et al. <i>Student Award</i>	Geostatistical and landscape analysis of fine-scale eelgrass (<i>Zostera marina</i>) habitat patterns	3	Wed, 16h20
Barrie et al.,	Inland Tidal Seas of the Northeastern Pacific	6	Tue, 17h40
Bax et al.,	Identifying ecologically and biologically significant deepwater habitat	4	Thu, 10h50
Bergersen et al.,	Application of an Integrated GIS and 4D Visualisation Tool Kit to the NIWA Cook Strait Data Set	1	Tue, 16h20
Black et al.,	A GIS analysis of New Zealand's Trawl Footprint	1	Tue, 14h50
Bourillet et al.,	Geomorphological characterisation of cold water corals habitats (Bay of Biscay, NE Atlantic)	3	Wed, 14h30
Bowden et al.,	Multibeam sonar in the deep-sea: can it really tell us much about benthic habitats and fauna?	1	Tue, 14h10
Brooke et al.,	Seabed diversity of the shelf surrounding Lord Howe Island	6	Tue, 17h40
Bürk et al.,	Seafloor sediment classification in a tidal inlet channel: The influence of shell debris and seafloor rugosity	1	Tue, 10h50
Canals et al.,	The Catalan submarine canyon heads, NW Mediterranean Sea: coupling seafloor morphology and biological diversity	3	Wed, 14h50
Clark et al., <i>Keynote speaker</i>	Habitat as a proxy for biodiversity: how can seamount classification systems aid the scientific design of marine protected areas	4	Thu, 8h30
Cogswell et al.,	Using GIS Models to Delimit Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem (VME) Boundaries in the Northwest Atlantic Regulatory Area (NRA)	4	Thu, 11h10
Collin et al.,	Spatial predictability of species diversity and abundance of epimacrobenthos in turbid nearshore using bathymetric LiDAR	2	Wed, 9h40
Colquhoun et al.,	Habitat-based assessment of epibenthos using AUV Optical imagery, northwest Australia	1	Tue, 14h30
D'angelo et al.,	Phanerogame meadows: a characteristic habitat of the Mediterranean shelf. Examples from the Tyrrhenian Sea	5	Thu, 14h50
De Mol et al.,	Predictive cold-water coral habitat mapping in the Western Mediterranean Sea	4	Thu, 11h30
De Mol et al.,	Alboran Seamounts, Western Mediterranean sea	6	Tue, 17h40
Diesing et al.,	Rocky reef in the central English Channel	6	Tue, 17h40
Dolan et al.,	Mapping and modelling seabed nature-types in Norway's MAREANO programme – lessons learned	5	Thu, 16h20
Downie et al.,	The Influence of Physical Parameters on Benthic Communities – A Case Study in the Gulf of Finland, the Baltic Sea	3	Thu, 9h20
Dunstan et al.,	Predicting Groups of Species: application of finite mixture models to species prediction	2	Wed, 13h30
Friedman et al., <i>Student Award</i>	Towards Automated Classification of Benthic Environments using Rugosity, Slope and Aspect from Bathymetric Stereo Image Reconstructions	2	Wed, 10h50
Gauthier et al.,	Quantifying trawling impacts on deep-sea ecosystems using ROV video and scanning-sonar data	3	Wed, 10h00
Gonzalez-Mirelis et al., <i>Student Award</i>	Deriving "mappable" biological assemblages from underwater footage using classification tree models	2	Wed, 11h30
Greene et al.,	Deep-Water Forage Habitats - The Next Step Forward in Marine Benthic Habitat Mapping?	1	Tue, 11h30
Greene et al.,	Outer Shelf Rocky Habitats of Alaska	6	Tue, 17h40
Heap et al.,	Seabed mapping for Australia's energy security	5	Thu, 14h10
Hewitt et al.,	Environmental classifications, acoustic remote assessment and ecosystem valuing	3	Wed, 13h50
Huang et al.,	Dynamics of benthic patch structure across two seasons in a coastal embayment	3	Wed, 16h40
Huvenne et al.,	A picture on the wall: 3D habitat mapping in deep-sea canyons	1	Tue, 9h40
Huvenne et al.,	Habitat heterogeneity in deep-sea canyons offshore Portugal	6	Tue, 17h40

Authors	Title	Session	Date / Time
James et al.,	Open shelf valley system, Northern Palaeovalley, English Channel, U.K.	6	Tue, 17h40
James et al.,	Sand wave field: The OBel Sands, Bristol Channel, U.K.	6	Tue, 17h40
Julian et al.,	Can oceanographic conditions explain species distribution patterns on the Chatham Rise and Challenger Plateau?	2	Wed, 9h00
Kingon <i>Student Award</i>	A system for mapping nearshore, marine habitats on a tight budget	1	Tue, 10h00
Klaucke et al.,	Geoacoustic mapping of cold seep habitats along the Hikurangi margin, New Zealand	1	Tue, 11h50
Kostylev et al.,	Seabed habitats of the Beaufort Sea Shelf (Canadian Arctic)	4	Thu, 12h10
Kotilainen et al.,	Glacial coastal formations, western Finland	6	Tue, 17h40
Lafoy et al.,	ZoNeCo: a multidisciplinary approach to Marine Habitats in New Caledonia	5	Thu, 16h00
Lamarche et al.,	The Cook Strait canyon, New Zealand: A large bedrock canyon system in a tectonically active environment.	6	Tue, 17h40
Lawton et al.,	Relationships between seabed assemblages in the Gulf of Maine and their physical environment using Random Forests	3	Wed, 16h00
Lee et al.,	Diversity in benthic habitats and sediments at Great Barrier Island, New Zealand	3	Wed, 14h10
Leon et al.,	A geospatial approach to coral reef geomorphology	1	Tue, 15h40
Leroy	Making Technology Transparent - A key to better science is spending more time studying the data than collecting it	1	Tue, 16h40
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